

422 cases of **non-small cell lung cancer** (NSCLC) from TCIA just for testing.

For these patients pretreatment CT scans, manual delineation by a radiation oncologist of the 3D volume of the gross tumor volume and clinical outcome data are available.

The original source is: <https://doi.org/10.7937/K9/TCIA.2015.PF0M9REI>

There you will find a detailed description.

There is no addition or change over the original dataset.

Data Citation:

Aerts, H. J. W. L., Wee, L., Rios Velazquez, E., Leijenaar, R. T. H., Parmar, C., Grossmann, P., Carvalho, S., Bussink, J., Monshouwer, R., Haibe-Kains, B., Rietveld, D., Hoebbers, F., Rietbergen, M. M., Leemans, C. R., Dekker, A., Quackenbush, J., Gillies, R. J., Lambin, P. (2014). Data From NSCLC-Radiomics (version 4) [Data set]. The Cancer Imaging Archive.

<https://doi.org/10.7937/K9/TCIA.2015.PF0M9REI>

ID: ba2a9990-97f1-4816-8789-c94e65d90c01

URL: <https://eucaim-node.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/ba2a9990-97f1-4816-8789-c94e65d90c01/details>

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Contact info.: <https://doi.org/10.7937/K9/TCIA.2015.PF0M9REI>

Studies count: 422

Subjects count: 422

Age range: Between 34 years and 88 years

Sex: Male, Female, Undifferentiated

Body part(s): LUNG, Unknown

Modality: RTSTRUCT, CT